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Doctoral Dissertation

Chromatin regulatory mechanism and its impact
on fungal development and secondary metabolism
in the *Fusarium fujikuroi* species complex

submitted by

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Affidavit

I hereby declare that I have authored this dissertation independently and that I have not used any assistance other than that which is permitted. The work contained herein is my own except where explicitly stated otherwise. All ideas taken in wording or in basic content from unpublished sources or from published literature are duly identified and cited, and precise references are included. Any contribution from colleagues is explicitly stated in the authorship statement of the published papers.

I further declare that this dissertation has not been submitted, in whole or in part, in the same or a similar form, to any other educational institution as part of the requirements for an academic degree.

I hereby confirm that I am familiar with the standards of Scientific Integrity and with the guidelines of Good Scientific Practice and that this work fully complies with these standards and guidelines.

Tulln an der Donau, 30.01.2025

Anna K. ATANASOFF-KARDJALIEFF (*manu propria*)

*"This thesis is dedicated to my family and friends,
who endlessly supported me through this journey of joy and tears"*

“As you read these words, fungi are changing the way life happens, as they have done for more than a billion years.”

Merlin Sheldrake, *Entangled Life*, 2020

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List of publications

Publications that are the main part of this cumulative dissertation

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6. **Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, A.K.**, Berger, H., Steinert, K., Janevska, S., Ponts, N., Humpf, H.-U., Kalinina, S. & Studt-Reinhold, L. Incorporation of the histone variant H2A.Z counteracts gene silencing mediated by H3K27 trimethylation in *Fusarium fujikuroi*. *Epigenetics & Chromatin*, **in revision**

Abstract

The genus *Fusarium* is a species-rich group of mycotoxigenic plant pathogens that are detrimental to modern agriculture. Fusaria are not only able to infect a wide range of economically important staple crops but also to produce a large portfolio of natural products (NPs). These include potent mycotoxins, contaminating food and feed sources and thereby threatening food security worldwide. A central position within the genus has the *Fusarium fujikuroi* species complex (FFSC), harboring important phytopathogens such as *Fusarium mangiferae*, *F. fujikuroi*, or *Fusarium proliferatum* able to cause several plant diseases. Various environmental or developmental cues trigger the rearrangements of the chromatin structure, thus altering the transcriptional output to react to these various changes. To achieve such, different mechanisms have been described, including the deposition of histone marks, the incorporation of histone variants, or the utilization of ATP-dependent chromatin-modifying complexes. Within this work, we functionally characterized two histone marks *i.e.*, H3K9me3 and H3K27me3, hallmarks of heterochromatin, as well as the histone variant H2A.Z. Within the first part of this work, we finally revealed the crosstalk between constitutive- (H3K9me3) and facultative (H3K27me3) heterochromatin also in this genus. Next, we utilized the H3K9me3-deletion mutant to show that two NPs, fusapyrone (FPY) and fusamarins (FMNs), prior not described to be produced by members of the FFSC, are biosynthesized by *F. mangiferae*. Moreover, we determined and dissected the biosynthetic gene clusters, PKS40 and PKS8, responsible for the biosynthesis of FPY and FMNs, respectively. Secondly, we revealed that the histone variant H2A.Z is essential in *Fusarium*, but by making use of a depletion mutant we determined the role of H2A.Z in *F. fujikuroi*. Here, we show that incorporation of H2A.Z at the +1-nucleosome facilitates positive gene transcription, occurring independent of the chromatin state.

Kurzfassung

Die Gattung *Fusarium* umfasst eine artenreiche Gruppe von Pflanzenpathogenen, welche höchst problematisch für die moderne Landwirtschaft sind. Hier gehören zu den ökonomisch wichtigen Vertretern unter anderem *Fusarium mangiferae*, *Fusarium fujikuroi* und *Fusarium proliferatum*, welche dem *Fusarium fujikuroi*-Spezies-Komplex (FFSK) zugeordnet sind. Generell können Fusarien nicht nur eine Vielzahl an Nutzpflanzen infizieren, sondern dabei auch hoch wirksame Naturprodukte (NP) bilden, welche zur Kontamination von wichtigen Nahrungs- und Futterquellen führt. Um auf Veränderung in der Umgebung zu reagieren, können verschiedene Umwelteinflüsse, mitunter die Infektion von Pflanzen, die Umstrukturierung der Chromatinstruktur verursachen, welches zu einer veränderten Gentranskription führt. Um dieses herbeizuführen, sind bereits verschiedene Mechanismen beschrieben, *i.e.*, die Positionierung von Histon Markierungen, der Einbau von Histonvarianten oder die Nutzung von ATP-abhängigen Chromatin-modifizierenden Komplexen. Im Rahmen dieser Arbeit charakterisierten wir zwei Histon Markierungen, die Kennzeichen von konstitutivem- (H3K9me3) sowie fakultativem (H3K27me3) Heterochromatin sind, sowie die Histon Variante H2A.Z. Hier zeigen wir als erstes, dass H3K9me3 sowie H3K27me3 auch in diesem Genus miteinander interagieren. Als nächstes konnten wir eine H3K9me3-Deletionsmutante nutzen und bestimmen, dass Fusapyron und Fusamarine, zwei NP, ebenfalls von Mitgliedern des FFSK produziert werden. Darüber hinaus konnten wir dessen biosynthetischen Gencluster aufklären und die an der Biosynthese involvierten Gene näher untersuchen. Als Nächstes zeigen wir, dass die Histonvariante H2A.Z in *Fusarium* essentiell ist, aber durch das generieren einer Knock-down-Mutante konnten wir die Rolle von H2A.Z in *F. fujikuroi* näher bestimmen. Hier zeigen wir, dass das Vorhandensein von H2A.Z am +1-Nukleosom die positive Gentranskription induziert und dass dieses unabhängig des Chromatinzustandes auftritt.

1 Introductory overview

1.1 *Fusarium*: a cosmopolitan genus

The genus *Fusarium* was first introduced more than two centuries ago by Link ^[1] and consists of a group of genetically diverse filamentous ascomycete fungi belonging to the class of Sordariomycetes ^[2]. Since then, more than 400 genetically diverse *Fusarium* species have been described and resolved in 23 species complexes ^[3, 4] with more isolates identified in the upcoming decades. *Fusarium* species have been isolated worldwide and shown to be “*bon vivant*” as they appear to have detrimental but also beneficial relationships within a large range of organisms.

Fusaria are typically known for their potential to infect a wide range of staple crops as well as horticultural plants, causing various disease symptoms resulting in significant losses annually ^[5]. *Fusarium* species from four distinct species complexes *i.e.*, the *Fusarium fujikuroi* species complex (FFSC), the *Fusarium graminearum* species complex (FGSC), the *Fusarium solani* species (FSSC) complex, and the *Fusarium oxysporum* species complex (FOSC) are considered to harbor the economically most important fungal species known to be detrimental for modern agriculture ^[4, 6]. It is not surprising that two species *i.e.*, *F. graminearum* and *F. oxysporum*, are found among the top ten most destructive fungal plant pathogens worldwide ^[7]. *Fusarium*-induced crop disease causes manifold symptoms such as root-, crown- or stem rots, cankers, wilts, fruit or seed rots, elongation and chlorosis depending on the colonized host system ^[8].

In general, most *Fusarium* species have a broad host range and may colonize more than a single host plant such as the FFSC member *Fusarium verticillioides* ^[9]. Although, predominantly associated with infected maize cobs, *F. verticillioides* has been isolated from numerous other economically important staple crops such as rice, sugarcane, wheat, banana, asparagus, and sorghum ^[10].

On the contrary, the FFSC member *Fusarium proliferatum* is not only known as a notorious plant pathogen on maize and asparagus but surprisingly some isolates are recovered from grasses, palms, and orchids without displaying disease symptoms indicating an endophytic relationship ^[11, 12]. Generally, an endophytic relationship is defined by the

colonization of plant tissue by certain microbes without causing adverse health effects or disease symptoms to the host plant. Some endophytes may even protect the colonized host from biotic and abiotic stresses throughout its life cycle ^[13]. Endophytic relationships are not only limited to *F. proliferatum* but are also described for *F. oxysporum*, *F. sacchari*, *F. solani*, and some other *Fusarium* isolates ^[14].

However, unlike most fusaria, the founding member of the FOOSC, *F. oxysporum*, is known to colonize a vast spectrum of both, monocotyledonous (e.g., banana or palm tree) and dicotyledonous plants (e.g., bean or tomato), but individual isolates display a remarkably high degree of host specificity. In consequence, isolates that are pathogenic on the same host are grouped in so-called *F. oxysporum formae speciales* ^[15]. This comprises for example *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *lycospersici* and *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *cubense* solely pathogenic on tomato and banana, respectively ^[16]. Thus far, 106 well-documented and 37 insufficiently documented *F. oxysporum formae speciales* have been described ^[17].

Furthermore, fusaria can not only occur as plant pathogens or non-pathogenic mutualists in several plants but also as symbionts of arthropods ^[18, 19]. Here, the relationship between *Fusarium* and the Asian longhorned beetle was intensively studied and highlighted the positive effects of *Fusarium* colonization on the beetle's nutrient acquisition ^[19]. Another study on ambrosia beetles unearthed that the non-pathogenic colonization by fusaria enables them to "hitchhike" until the beetle colonizes a susceptible host plant resulting in various *Fusarium*-borne diseases ^[20]. However, few studies revealed that fusaria are not only obligate arthropod mutualists, a few *Fusarium* species exhibit entomopathogenic behavior and were able to colonize various arthropods naturally ^[18, 21].

Fusarium-induced disease is not restricted to plants and arthropods, some species are described to cause disease, so-called fusariosis, in humans and animals ^[22]. The most prevalent symptoms in immunocompetent individuals comprise onychomycosis and keratitis, while immunocompromised individuals suffer from a high risk of invasive infections causing adverse severe health effects in those patients ^[23]. Several *Fusarium* species are described to be clinically relevant with *F. solani* most common followed by *F. oxysporum* and *F. proliferatum*. Moreover, the rising resistance of individual *Fusarium* strains against antifungals causes severe difficulties in individual patient treatment and overall results in high rates of mortality ^[24].

To conclude, *Fusarium* is a widely distributed cosmopolitan genus, found within diverse environments ranging from plants to arthropods and further to humans and animals as summarized in **Figure 1**. Fusaria are generally characterized as hemibiotrophic, though they can adapt to different lifestyles, including saprophytic-, biotrophic-, necrotrophic- or mutualistic growth, which all have been observed in the past. This renders this genus one of the most versatile within the fungal kingdom and demonstrates a huge genetic capability to adapt to various habitats.

Excerpt of the *Fusarium* cosmos

Figure 1 Excerpt of *Fusarium* species and their ecological niches. Phytopathogenic fusaria and their main host are highlighted within the green box, while symbionts and mutualistic *Fusarium* species and hosts are shown in the orange box. Fusaria known to cause eye and skin disease are depicted in the purple box. The figure was generated with the help of Biorender.com.

1.2 *Fusarium's* race to arms: An arsenal of natural products

The genus *Fusarium* is not only known for its widespread ecological roles, but fusaria have an enormous genetic potential to synthesize an arsenal of small molecular weight compounds so-called natural products (NPs), or secondary metabolites (SMs). Unlike primary metabolites, NPs are not strictly required for fungal growth and development *per se* ^[25] but may influence fungal physiology as shown earlier in the case of *Fusarium* reproduction ^[26]. The biosynthesis of NPs is triggered by certain environmental or developmental changes, including biotic and abiotic stressors such as shifts in the ambient pH, fluctuation in lights, competition in the acquisition of nutrients or habitats, or within the process of host colonization. Thus, the biosynthesis of NPs typically results in a selective advantage of the producing organism ^[27, 28].

1.2.1 The principles of fungal natural product biosynthesis

For the biosynthesis of NPs, the fungus takes advantage of the availability of a diverse set of basic building blocks from central metabolic pathways or primary metabolite pools ^[28]. In general, fungal NP biosynthesis can be roughly classified into four major classes of distinct key enzymes *i.e.*, polyketide synthases (PKSs), non-ribosomal peptide synthetases (NRPSs), terpene synthases (TSs), and dimethylallyltryptophane synthases (DMATSs) or hybrids thereof, giving rise to an immense and yet largely untapped chemical diversity within this genus ^[9, 29]. The different key enzymes are mainly distinguished by their highly conserved domain assembly. In more detail, PKSs and NRPSs are considered large multimodular megasynthases, which make use of acetyl-CoA moieties and amino acids as starter units, respectively ^[30, 31]. In contrast, TSs and DMATSs are relatively small enzymes. Here, TSs utilize C₅-activated isoprene units, while DMATSs use tryptophan, tyrosine, or indole ring-containing aromatic compounds as substrates^[32].

Next to this, fusaria harbor also the genetic potential to synthesize NPs *via* unusual enzymatic pathways. NRPS-like enzymes are characterized as mono- or bi-modular proteins, lacking typical NRPS modules, and seem not to utilize amino acids as starter units ^[33]. Recently, ribosomally synthesized and post-translationally modified peptides (RiPPs) caught the attention of a large body of research, including the genus *Fusarium*. Here, six RiPP-like encoding genes were detected in the re-sequenced genome of *F. proliferatum* ^[34]. In general,

the production of RiPPs is facilitated by the biosynthesis of core peptides, which is followed by various post-translational modification (PTM) steps giving rise to a huge variety of peptide-based NPs [35]. Next to this, cyclodipeptide synthases (CDPSs) synthesize cyclic organic compounds *via* the condensation of two activated amino acid moieties as substrates [36]. Thus far, no NRPS-like-, RiPP- or CDPS-derived NP from *Fusarium* has been identified.

In **Figure 2**, selected NPs derived from *Fusarium* are depicted, and sorted into their different chemical classes.

Figure 2 Prominent natural products (NPs) produced by members of the genus *Fusarium*. Polyketide synthase (PKS)-derived NPs are depicted in the blue box, metabolites produced by non-ribosomal peptide synthases (NRPSs) are shown in the purple box, while NPs derived from PKS-NRPS hybrids are depicted in the green box. Lastly, terpene synthase (TS)- and dimethylallyltryptophane synthase (DMATS) derived- metabolites are highlighted in the orange and yellow boxes, respectively.

1.2.2 The principles of fungal polyketide biosynthesis

Polyketides produced by filamentous fungi own remarkably high structural diversity as well as a wide range of biological functions. Therefore, it is not surprising that various classes of fungal PKSs exist. In general, filamentous fungi, including fusaria may harbor two types of PKSs *i.e.*, type I PKSs and type III PKSs, while type II PKSs are restricted to the kingdom of bacteria ^[37]. Type III PKSs are rarely found within the genus *Fusarium*, while type I PKSs are prevalent ^[38]. Briefly, while type III PKSs are similar to plant chalcone synthases, solely consisting of a single keto synthase (KS) domain ^[39], type I PKSs are characterized by their distinct domain organization. Depending on the catalytic domain composition, type I PKSs can be further classified as highly reducing (HR), partially reducing (PR), and non-reducing (NR) PKSs, which in turn dictates the polyketide chemical structure ^[40]. Moreover, type I PKSs function in a highly iterative fashion giving rise to a myriad of chemically diverse structures.

Overall, minimal PKSs consist of three distinct catalytically active domains *i.e.*, an acyltransferase domain (AT), a KS domain, and an acyl carrier protein (ACP). Each of these domains is programmed to perform vital roles during biosynthesis. First, the AT domain selectively recognizes the reaction starter- and extender units. As starter units usually an acetate residue derived from acetyl-CoA is utilized, while extender units are malonate units derived from malonyl-CoA ^[30,41]. Recently it has been shown that some AT domains can accept alternative small substrates. For example, benzoate or propionate serve as substrates to initiate polyketide biosynthesis, while chain extension is facilitated using chloroethylmalonate or hexylmalonate moieties ^[42]. Then, the AT domain catalyzes the transfer of the initial substrate to the KS domain, which is essential to perform the C-C bond formation *via* successive Claisen condensation reactions. However, before the KS domain can initiate chain condensation, the AT domain transfers the extender unit to the ACP. The ACP domain then is responsible for shuttling the basic building blocks and consequently the emerging polyketide intermediates between the PKS's distinct domains ^[30,41].

As mentioned before, type I PKSs are distinguished by their overall domain organization. Here, NR-PKS are characterized by the presence of the three minimal PKS domains as well as a starter-unit acyltransferase (SAT) and a product template domain (PT) ^[43]. While the SAT domain activates and provides the starter unit for polyketide biosynthesis, the PT domain seems to enhance the product cyclization and dehydration chemistry of certain

polyketides ^[41, 44]. Next to this, NR-PKS can harbor additional domains such as an intrinsic C-methyltransferase (CMet) domain, a thioesterase (TE) domain, a Claisen cyclase (CLC) or reductase (R), primarily involved in the release of the mature product from the PKS as depicted in **Figure 3** ^[44]. Typically, NR-PKSs are involved in the biosynthesis of (poly)aromatic compounds such as the pigments fusarubin ^[45] and bikaverin ^[46] in *Fusarium*.

In contrast, HR-PKSs synthesize NPs characterized by aliphatic chains or rings, depending on the release mechanism. Here, in addition to the minimal PKS domains, HR-PKSs harbor domains that are responsible for the step-wise reduction of the keto groups or modification of the emerging chain ^[47]. In detail, the reduction of carbonyl groups is facilitated by a ketoreductase (KR) domain, while saturated bonds can undergo dehydration to form unsaturated bonds *via* a dehydratase (DH) domain. Then, the reduction of unsaturated bonds can be performed by an enoyl reductase (ER) domain in *cis* or *trans*. Lastly, HR-PKS may harbor an intrinsic CMet domain able to attach a methyl group from S-adenosylmethionine (SAM) to the emerging polyketide chain ^[30, 40]. The typical domains of HR-PKSs are shown in **Figure 3**. The polyketide offloading is then facilitated *via* discrete proteins, spontaneous release, or additional domains located at the C-terminal end of the PKS. Typical PKS release domains comprise a thioesterase (TE) domain, which facilitates offload *via* hydrolysis or transesterification, or a carnitine O-acyltransferase (CT)-domain, involved in the direct transesterification of the polyketide ^[48].

Figure 3 Domain organization of fungal type I- and type III polyketide synthases (PKSs). The minimal domains for a functional type I PKS comprise a keto synthase (KS)-, an acyl transferase (AT)- and an acyl carrier protein (ACP) domain. Type I highly-reducing (HR)-PKSs harbor additional reducing domains including a dehydratase (DH)-, and keto reductase (KR) domain. Optionally HR-PKSs can include an intrinsic enoyl reductase (ER)- or C-methyltransferase (CMet) domain as well as a carnitine O-acyltransferase (CT) domain for the product release. NR-PKSs are characterized by a starter-unit acyltransferase (SAT)- and product template (PT) domain. To facilitate the release of the polyketide backbone, NR-PKS can harbor a thioesterase (TE)-, Claisen cyclase (CLC)-, CMet-, or reductase (R) domain. In contrast, type III PKSs consist only of a functional KS domain.

1.2.3 It is all about the genetics: Fungal biosynthetic gene clusters

Notably, fungal NP biosynthesis can be more complex than initially anticipated. After the final release of the NP from the respective key enzyme, the NP backbone may be subject to further post-tailoring modifications *via* so-called tailoring enzymes. Tailoring enzymes can install a variety of functional groups within the NP backbone, *e.g.*, glycosylation, oxygenation, or methylation^[49] further shaping the chemical wealth of fungal NPs. Generally, genes involved in post-NP tailoring are located in close vicinity to the respective key enzyme gene, finally forming a so-called biosynthetic gene cluster (BGC)^[50]. Here, the close spatial proximity enables the co-regulation of the genes. Next to this, another important layer of regulation comprises transcriptional factors (TFs) or transporters encoded within the same BGC. While TFs are able to regulate the gene expression of individual genes encoded within a BGC, transporters may be vital to protect the fungus from self-intoxication *via* several mechanisms^[51]. Thus these proteins are able to orchestrate the biosynthesis of NPs in a precisely coordinated manner^[52]. **Figure 4** depicts the typical organization of a fungal BGC.

Figure 4 Typical elements of a fungal biosynthetic gene cluster (BGC) involved in natural product (NP) biosynthesis. Fungal BGCs may consist of various elements involved in product maturation. Here, usually, a NP-key enzyme is present *i.e.*, a polyketide synthase (PKS), a non-ribosomal peptide synthetase (NRPS), a terpene synthase (TS), or a dimethylallyltryptophane synthase (DMATS), which are depicted in the green box. Next to the key enzyme, a BGC may harbor regulatory elements such as a transcription factor (TF) or a Major Facilitator Superfamily (MFS)-type transporter (light-blue boxes) or a set of tailoring enzymes involved in post-NP biosynthesis tailoring (blue boxes). Black boxes depict the BGCs neighboring genes, not involved in the NP biosynthesis. The arrows indicate a hypothetical direction of transcription.

It is noteworthy to mention that there is no general rule applicable, for determining a minimum or maximum of genes involved in NP biosynthesis. For example in the case of *Fusarium*, the BGC involved in the biosynthesis of gibepyrone consists of only two genes *i.e.*, an NP-key enzyme-encoding gene *PKS13 (GPY1)* producing the final product and a Zn(2)-C6 fungal-type transcription factor (TF, *GPY2*), positively influencing gibepyrone biosynthesis ^[53]. In contrast, biosynthesis of fusapyrone (FPY) and deoxyfusapyrone (dFPY) is facilitated by a seven-gene BGC (*FPY1-FPY7*), consisting next to the key enzyme-encoding gene *PKS40*, of a variety of different genes encoding *e.g.*, a glycosyltransferase an oxidoreductase and a Major Facilitator Superfamily (MFS)-type transporter ^[54]. However, it is noteworthy to mention that even larger BGC exist, such as the aflatoxin BGC, found in several filamentous fungi mostly belonging to the class of *Aspergillus*. Here, aflatoxin biosynthesis is facilitated by a 30-gene BGC ^[55].

In general, the presence of BGCs within fungal genomes, and modern genome sequencing technologies combined with sophisticated bioinformatic algorithms allow the prediction of a sheer variety of fungal BGCs yet to be explored, especially within the genus *Fusarium* ^[56].

1.3 The *Fusarium fujikuroi* species complex and its global impact at a glance

Within the genus *Fusarium*, one of the most well-studied species complexes is the FFSC, due to its general relevance in the agricultural- and recently the clinical sector. The FFSC includes more than 60 genetically distinct species^[9, 57] clustered in three phylogenetic clades *i.e.*, the African-, the Asian-, and the American clade^[58]. Each clade is characterized by *Fusarium* species highly diverse in the patho- and chemotype.

Within the Asian clade *F. fujikuroi*, the namesake of the FFSC is known as a notorious pathogen of rice causing 'bakanae' (foolish seedling disease)^[59] or stunting of rice seedlings, depending on the isolate's ability to produce a specific cocktail of NPs during the infection process^[60]. The plant disease is of increasing economic importance, due to drastic forfeitures in harvest^[61] in all rice-growing countries in the southern hemisphere^[62]. Next to *F. fujikuroi*, *F. mangiferae* is also found within the Asian clade, though characterized by the ability to solely infect mango trees or seedlings instead of staple crops. Thus, *F. mangiferae* is the causal agent of the so-called mango malformation disease (MMD)^[63] resulting in vegetative malformations on mango seedlings and young flowering trees^[64], consequently leading to devastating economic losses annually^[65]. Notably, both species seem to utilize the phytohormones gibberellins (GAs) during infection, though this seems to underly different mechanisms^[38, 66]. Next to this, the African- and Asian clade members *F. verticillioides* and *F. proliferatum*, respectively, are both known for their remarkably broad but similar host range on cereals^[12]. Both species are considered causal agents of the *Fusarium* ear rot of maize^[67], with *F. verticillioides* more prevalent^[12]. Nonetheless, a hallmark of both species is the production of the highly potent fumonisin B mycotoxins (FBs) during *in planta* growth^[8, 68]. Regular dietary exposure to FBs is highly associated with cancer and other health defects in mammals^[69]. Though *F. fujikuroi* and other members of the FFSC harbor the BGC involved in FBs biosynthesis, *F. fujikuroi* produces only minor amounts compared to *F. verticillioides* under laboratory conditions^[9, 70]. However, it is noteworthy to mention that most of the *F. fujikuroi* isolates do not produce FBs during pathogenic growth on rice, except some isolates including *F. fujikuroi* B14 causing stunting instead of elongation of seedlings^[60]. In general, members of the FFSC are highly mycotoxigenic fungi owning a similar genetic potential to produce a mixture of economically important mycotoxins including, the aforementioned FBs^[71, 72], fusaric

acid (FUB) ^[72, 73], moniliformin (MON) ^[74], beauvericin (BEA) ^[75], fusaproliferin (FUP) ^[76], fusarins (FUS) ^[72] and enniatins ^[77]. However, not all NPs produced by members of the FFSC are detrimental to modern agriculture but assume other ecosystem services. For example, FPY has been shown to harbor widespread antifungal activity ^[78] and could even serve as a potential biocontrol agent in vineyards ^[79]. Next to this, some of the dihydroisocoumarin derivatives fusamarins (FMNs), are described to have widespread functions such as antimalarial, anti-tuberculosis, and anti-fungal activities while exhibiting moderate cytotoxicity against human liver- and colon cancer cells ^[80, 81]. In average, fusaria roughly possess 50 individual BGCs putatively involved in NP biosynthesis ^[56]. Unfortunately, only a fraction of NPs have been identified yet and even a smaller number of them are linked to their respective BGC. Thus far, efforts to elucidate the full chemo metabolome of members of the FFSC are still limited by favorable laboratory conditions and the lack of known stimuli mimicking natural conditions to trigger NP biosynthesis. Besides environmental cues, the biosynthesis of individual NPs highly depends on the type of isolate ^[9, 60], already implying a complex gene regulatory network involved in the expression and thus biosynthesis of fungal NPs.

1.4 Chromatin: A powerful tool to control gene transcription

In every eukaryotic cell nucleus, DNA is present in a highly condensed state to protect, maintain, and manage the accessibility of DNA in a spatially and temporally coordinated manner. In general, all DNA-dependent processes in the eukaryotic nucleus are chromatin-dependent, *i.e.*, DNA replication, DNA repair, gene transcription, or the 3D organization of the chromosomes in the interphase and during mitosis and meiosis ^[82]. This is only possible through the tight association of the DNA with the highly conserved canonical histone proteins H2A, H2B, H3, and H4. In detail, approximately 147 bp of DNA is tightly wound around an octamer of core histones, termed nucleosomes, which are further condensed to form the basic packaging form of DNA: Chromatin ^[83]. However, chromatin is more than the mere basic packaging form of DNA, it is a highly dynamic scaffold serving as a versatile platform for the transcriptional machinery by responding to various environmental and developmental cues and thereby regulating the accessibility of DNA.

1.4.1 A continuum of accessibility states decides the transcriptional fate

Depending on the degree of compaction, chromatin can be classified into two states, *i.e.*, euchromatin or heterochromatin. In general, euchromatin is considered the “loosely packed” form of chromatin, which is available for the transcriptional machinery and thus these genomic regions are characterized by gene transcription. In contrast, heterochromatin is considered the “highly condensed” form of chromatin and in consequence largely inaccessible to the transcriptional machinery resulting in subdued or no transcriptional output. Heterochromatin can be further classified into two distinct groups, depending on their overall dynamics *i.e.*, facultative- and constitutive heterochromatin ^[84]. Here, the non-dynamic, constitutive heterochromatin is mainly enriched in gene-poor regions. Thus, mostly present in genomic regions such as telomers or centromeres important for providing structural stability or silencing parasitic transposable elements ^[85, 86]. While, facultative heterochromatin is mostly present in gene-rich regions, which can be subjected to remodeling *i.e.*, “normally” silent regions can be reversibly made accessible for the transcriptional machinery and thus poised for gene transcription ^[84]. The principal states of accessibility of the chromatin structure are depicted in **Figure 5**.

Figure 5 Schematic depiction of the transcriptional machinery non-accessible (heterochromatin) and accessible state (euchromatin) of chromatin. In the red box the largely inaccessible form of chromatin is depicted *i.e.*, heterochromatin. Within the green box, the accessible and mainly transcriptional active euchromatin is highlighted. ORF, open reading frame; Pol II, RNA polymerase II.

Thus, chromatin may serve as a substrate or a natural obstacle for the transcriptional machinery being fundamental for the timely-coordinated expression of a large set of genes.

1.5 The guardians of transcription: Chromatin-modifying proteins

Chromatin exists in discrete forms *i.e.*, euchromatin and heterochromatin, leaving the underlying genes poised and blocked for transcription, respectively. To establish either chromatin state, and thus shape the transcriptional output of the chromatin landscape, four already well-described regulatory circuits are known *i.e.*, the post-translational modification of N-terminal histone tails, DNA methylation, the exchange of canonical histones against histone variants as well as the rearrangement of the higher nucleosome organization by ATP-dependent chromatin remodeling enzyme complexes. The principal functions and actions of chromatin are visualized in **Figure 6**.

1.5.1 Histone post-translational modifications of N-terminal tails

In 1964, Allfrey's pioneering studies proposed for the first time that histone N-terminal tails, which protrude from every histone core, can be subjected to post-translational modifications (histone PTMs or histone marks) ^[87], and with that he heralded a new era in the field of genetics. In general, a plethora of different moieties such as acetyl-, methyl-, phosphate-, or ubiquitin groups can be covalently attached to distinct amino acid residues (*e.g.*, lysine, arginine) at the histone N-terminal tails. Depending on the type of covalent

modification as well as the quantity attached (at least in the case of methyl groups), the chromatin structure is subjected to condensation or opening and thus will either be accessible or blocked for the transcriptional machinery ^[84, 88].

To maintain the transcriptional balance in cells, it is equally important to establish, read, and relay as well as to remove these individual signals received *via* interconnected signaling pathways. In detail, enzymes involved in the formation, recognition, and removal of particular histone marks are called “writer”, “reader” and “eraser” proteins, respectively. While “writer” enzymes can covalently attach distinct chemical groups on the histone tails, “eraser” enzymes oppose these functions by catalyzing the removal of the prior installed moiety. However, to further convey the received signal “reader” proteins can recognize and bind to histone marks *via* distinct domains, providing a potential platform for other anchoring proteins able to initiate the signaling pathway ^[89]. Thus, these different classes of enzymes facilitate the establishment of the highly dynamic “histone code” ^[90], which in turn regulates the accessibility of the chromatin structure hence DNA-templated processes ^[91].

1.5.1.1 Methylation of histone tails: One residue many transcriptional fates

One of the most well-described histone marks is the methylation of lysine residues on histone H3. Here, the covalent attachment of one up to three methyl residues on a single lysine residue can induce multifaceted functional consequences to the chromatin scaffold.

Deposition of methyl residues is generally facilitated by histone lysine methyltransferases (histone KMTs) a class of proteins characterized by their catalytic domain *i.e.*, the SET-domain ((**Su**(var)3-9), **E**nhancer of zeste (E(z)), and **T**rithorax). The SET domain is responsible for the transfer of one or more methyl groups from SAM to a lysine residue on a histone N-terminal tail or another protein ^[92]. Thus far, only one protein is known, able to transfer a methyl group to a lysine residue on H3, without utilizing a SET domain *i.e.*, Dot1p ^[93].

While histone acetylation is merely correlated with active gene transcription the picture is more complex in the case of histone methylation. Depending on the selective action of the histone KMT, histone methylation can result in different transcriptional fates depending on its position and degree of methylation ^[94]. Here, trimethylation of histone H3 lysine 9 (H3K9me3)

and histone H3 lysine 27 (H3K27me3) can be roughly associated with the formation of constitutive- (static) and facultative (dynamic) heterochromatin, respectively. In contrast histone H3 lysine 4 trimethylation (H3K4me3) is correlated with active gene transcription, this is also true in the case of filamentous fungi, including *Fusarium* [34, 54, 95-98]. However, the trimethylation of histone H3 lysine 36 (H3K36me3) seems to function as a bivalent mark, at least in the case of *F. fujikuroi*, *Zyoseptoria tritici*, and *Neurospora crassa* [99, 100]. Here, unlike shown for the yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* [101], two SET domain-containing proteins are required to establish H3K36me3 *i.e.*, Ash1 and Set2 (Kmt3) as shown for *F. fujikuroi*, *N. crassa* and *Z. tritici*. Though both proteins install the same histone mark, they target different genomic regions *i.e.*, Ash1 predominately targets subtelomeric regions characterized by silent or poorly transcribed genes, while Set2 mediates H3K36me3 at genomic loci located at gene bodies associated with active gene transcription [99, 100].

1.5.2 DNA methylation

Not only histone N-terminal tails can be subjected to methylation by specific enzymes but also the DNA template can undergo methylation events at distinct regions. Here, DNA methylation is catalyzed by different DNA methyltransferases (DNMTs), which are able to covalently attach a methyl moiety from the donor unit SAM, to the C5 position on a cytosine base [102]. Generally, DNA methylation is considered a stable repressive mark, assuming pivotal roles in cell biology in higher organisms [103]. In filamentous fungi, DNA methylation assumes manifold functions, such as being involved in the establishment of genome defense mechanisms against parasitic elements in the case of *N. crassa* [104]. Furthermore, normal DNA methylation patterns are required for normal fungal development in the plant pathogenic fungus *Magnaportha oryzae* as well as for pathogenicity and NP biosynthesis in the case of *F. graminearum* [105].

1.5.3 Histone variants

As mentioned before, DNA is tightly wrapped around an octamer of canonical histone proteins (nucleosome) to protect, maintain, and manage all DNA-dependent processes in the eukaryotic nucleus. Here, the canonical histones H2A, H2B, H3, and H4 primarily assume functions in genome packaging and gene regulation, and their expression is tightly linked to DNA replication ^[106]. However, canonical histones can be replaced by non-canonical histones *i.e.*, histone variants. Genes encoding histone variants are expressed throughout the cell cycle and significantly differ in their amino acid sequence, compared to their canonical paralogues. Thus, the exchange of canonical histones against histone variants can influence the nucleosome structure, -dynamics, or -stability ultimately resulting in altered DNA accessibility and chromatin function. Histone variants are known to assume a myriad of different functions, including being vital for DNA double-strand repair, transcription initiation or termination, cell cycle progression, chromosome stability and segregation, or, epigenetic memory ^[107].

1.5.3.1 The histone variant H2A.Z. – conserved but controversial

The histone variant H2A.Z is one of the best-studied non-canonical histones known. Yet no universal role is assigned to H2A.Z incorporation among eukaryotes, thus the presence of H2A.Z is still controversial and widely discussed. Deletion of *H2A.Z* is essential in most higher organisms, including *Fusarium* ^[108] implying pivotal roles in cell biology. However, H2A.Z is dispensable for budding and fission yeasts and the ascomycete fungus *N. crassa* ^[109, 110].

Thus far, several gene regulatory functions could be assigned to H2A.Z such as induction and silencing of gene expression, DNA repair and replication, chromosome stability, epigenetic memory, or cell cycle progression, again depending on the tested organism ^[109, 111, 112]. Moreover, H2A.Z has been shown to bridge several boundaries between euchromatin and heterochromatin formation and gene expression in plants, *N. crassa*, and mammalian cells ^[113-116].

1.5.4 ATP-dependent chromatin remodeling complexes

Last but not least, to ensure a dynamic balance between higher genome organization and its accessibility, another regulatory mechanism is well-described. Here, highly specialized ATP-dependent enzyme complexes or “remodelers” can rearrange the nucleosome composition at certain genomic regions to modify the chromatin's overall accessibility. Thus, remodelers utilize the energy of ATP-hydrolysis to facilitate alteration in the chromatin composition by sliding, ejecting, adding, or rearranging nucleosomes ^[117]. These particular perturbations may result in a “fluid chromatin state” in which designated sequences are transiently exposed to certain factors, including the transcriptional machinery ^[118].

Moreover, some remodelers may not act alone, but in concert with certain histone marks or histone variants ^[119]. The crosstalk between different chromatin-modifying circuits is common and introduces another highly complex regulatory layer to safeguard transcriptional processes.

Figure 6 Schematic overview of chromatin-modifying mechanisms. On the top, the posttranslational modification of histone N-terminal tails (histone marks) is depicted. Here, two prominent histone marks are the histone H3 lysine 4- (H3K4) and histone H3 lysine 27 (H3K27) trimethylation (me3) facilitating gene transcription and gene silencing, respectively are shown. However, various histone marks are described resulting in different transcriptional outputs. In the middle row, the exchange of a non-canonical histone variant (H2A.Z) and a canonical histone (H2A) is depicted. The transcriptional fate after the incorporation of H2A.Z highly depends on the organism investigated. In the next row, a schematic depiction of a DNA strand including DNA methylation at cytosine residues (green dot). Lastly, at the bottom row, ATP-dependent chromatin remodeling complexes are depicted. This class of enzymes can remove, slide, or add nucleosomes to the chromatin structure, thereby modifying the accessibility of the DNA scaffold and thus the transcriptional output.

1.6 Discussion

1.6.1 Connecting the dots: Chromatin regulatory mechanism and the FFSC

The genus *Fusarium* is characterized by its multifaceted ecological roles. However, one central part of the FFSC within the genus *Fusarium* is, that many species and their associated NPs are detrimental to modern agriculture. Here, the FFSC harbors several mycotoxigenic isolates including *F. fujikuroi*, *F. proliferatum*, and *F. mangiferae*, responsible for several disastrous plant diseases on important staple crops. In light of this, it is equally important to understand the fundamentals of fungal development and NP biosynthesis and at the same time to exploit the full chemical potential hidden within fusaria's genomes to develop novel cropping strategies. As the biosynthesis of NPs is often hampered by favorable laboratory conditions it is evident that a complex gene regulatory network is involved in their expression. Several chromatin regulatory mechanisms have already been well-described in several model organisms. These results rapidly advanced our understanding of the gene regulatory networks and their role in *Fusarium*. Here, acetylation and methylation of histone N-termini have been subject to various studies, which have been reviewed recently ^[120], (Paper II). In this literature review, the role of chromatin regulatory circuits and NP biosynthesis has been summarized and extensively discussed to demonstrate the often-neglected importance of this topic. However, the overall picture is not yet complete, then not all regulatory proteins and their associated functions have been elucidated. Moreover, the putative crosstalk between histone marks, histone variants, or ATP-dependent chromatin-modifying enzymes, adds another layer of complexity to this topic.

Thus, all of the above-described chromatin regulatory mechanisms (and of course many more), form a complex gene regulatory cosmos yet waiting to be further entangled.

1.6.1.1 The Known and the Unknown: The role of heterochromatin and the histone variant H2A.Z within the FFSC

Constitutive heterochromatin is considered transcriptionally inert and assumes vital roles in chromosomal stability and silencing. A hallmark of constitutive heterochromatin is H3K9me3, which is mediated by the SET domain-containing enzyme Kmt1^[85, 121]. In fungi the Kmt1 orthologs, SpClr4 in *Schizosaccharomyces pombe*^[122], EclrD in *Epichloë festucae*^[123], BcDim5 in *Botrytis cinerea*^[124], AnclrD in *A. nidulans*^[125], NcDIM-5 in *N. crassa*^[126], MoKmt1 in *M. oryzae*^[127] and ZtKmt1 in *Z. tritici*^[128] are responsible to install this mark. H3K9me3 and thus constitutive heterochromatin is localized to telomeric-, centromeric- and repeat-rich genomic areas or in the case of *A. nidulans* flanking BGCs, as shown earlier^[86, 129]. In general, the trimethylation of H3K9me3 and its role in heterochromatin is well-explored in fungi, however, even if similar, functions and regulatory pathways are implied, its overall role highly depends on the fungi investigated, this is also true for the genus *Fusarium*.

Within, the FFSC the deposition of trimethylated histone H3K9 is also facilitated by Kmt1 as shown for *F. mangiferae*, *F. proliferatum*, and *F. verticillioides*^[34, 54, 98] (Paper I & V). Localization studies in two members of the FFSC, *i.e.*, *F. proliferatum* and *F. fujikuroi*, using chromatin Immunoprecipitation with subsequent sequencing (ChIP-seq) confirmed that H3K9me3 is predominantly established at telomeric and centromeric regions but also in few blocks located in intergenic regions^[34, 38] (Paper V). Functional characterizations of this histone mark regarding NP biosynthesis revealed that the lack of the respective Kmt1 ortholog resulted in only subtle changes. Here, for *F. verticillioides* increased expression of two melanin biosynthesis-related genes and FB₁ biosynthesis was observed. *F. mangiferae* only displayed increased beauvericin levels, while the biosynthesis of other measured metabolites remained wild-type-like^[54, 98] (Paper I). Though, biosynthesis of two other metabolites *i.e.*, FPY and FMNs, respectively were negatively influenced by the loss of FmKmt1 in *F. mangiferae*^[54, 81] (Paper I & III). Noteworthy, this observation is unlike expected, since the putative loss of heterochromatin should intuitively result in elevated biosynthesis of NPs. Unfortunately, at this time the promiscuity of the H3K9me3-specific antibody prohibited further localization studies and thus to draw further conclusions of this histone mark in *F. mangiferae*. However, given the circumstance that constitutive heterochromatin is absent from BGCs in the nearly *related* *F. fujikuroi* and *F. proliferatum*^[34, 38] (Paper V), the direct involvement of this histone mark in

fungal NP biosynthesis is unlikely. It is noteworthy to mention, that even if this histone mark is not directly involved in the biosynthesis of fungal NPs, with the aid of the *FmKMT1* deletion strain we were able to pinpoint the two NPs, *i.e.*, FPY and FMNs, prior unknown to be produced by members of the FFSC, to *F. mangiferae*. Thus, wild-type-like H3K9me3 is required for normal NP biosynthesis. Here, the comprehensive bioinformatic dissection of the putative key enzymes of FPY and FMNs revealed that both NPs originate from the HR-PKSs FmPKS40, and FmPKS8, respectively. Next to this, we could elucidate the respective BGCs by expressional studies for FPY and in the case of FMNs *via* gene expression and gene deletion experiments. In the case of FMNs, we were even able to propose a biosynthetic pathway. Next to this, by performing comparative genomics analysis we could show, that the FPY BGC is not only present in some members of the FFSC but also in other *Fusarium* isolates including members of the *Fusarium nisikadoi*-, *concolor*-, *lateritium*-, and *incarnatum-equisiti* species complex. Similar to this, a functional FMN BGC is also present in *F. oxysporum*. Subsequent expressional analysis of *FPY1*, the FPY biosynthesis key enzyme, in for *F. mangiferae*-inducing conditions revealed that only *F. mangiferae* was able to express *FPY1*, despite *F. fujikuroi* B14, *F. proliferatum* ET1, and *F. verticillioides* M3125 harboring a complete BGC. It seems that these isolates must receive different environmental or developmental stimuli to facilitate gene expression of *FPY1*. Next to this, for *FMN* expression, cultivation of *F. verticillioides* under *F. mangiferae*-inducing conditions led to the expression and biosynthesis of FMNs in this species, pointing toward a conserved signal. These analyses marked not only a step toward unraveling *Fusarium*'s vastly hidden chemical potential but also demonstrated that NPs are not universally expressed ^[54, 81] (Paper I & III). Next to this, the deletion of *KMT1* resulted in only minor growth and developmental retardations in *F. mangiferae*, *F. verticillioides*, and *F. proliferatum* alike ^[34, 54, 98] (Paper I & V) Surprisingly, *KMT1* seems to be essential in the nearly related *F. fujikuroi* ^[95]. This raises the fundamental question if there is a different or additional function of Kmt1 in *F. fujikuroi* compared to other *Fusarium* species.

One possible explanation for the observed effect could be, the complex interplay, between constitutive heterochromatin and facultative heterochromatin. Crosstalk between both marks was already shown earlier in several other fungal species including, *N. crassa*, *Z. tritici*, and *Podospora anserina* ^[128, 130]. However, until recently investigation of this phenomenon within the FFSC was hampered by the lethality of the mutants lacking the histone

H3 lysine 27 trimethyltransferase Kmt6^[95]. Trimethylation of H3K27 is a hallmark of facultative heterochromatin, predominantly covering large genomic regions enriched in BGCs involved in NP biosynthesis. Here, we could show that Kmt6 and thus H3K27me3 is dispensable for *F. proliferatum*. Making use of the availability of both deletion mutants *i.e.*, *KMT1* and *KMT6*, we revealed that H3K27me3 can rescue the loss of H3K9me3 but not *vice versa*. This may explain the subtle phenotype observed in the *KMT1* deletion strain in *F. proliferatum*^[34] (Paper V). Now it is intriguing to speculate that the loss of H3K9me3 cannot be rescued by H3K27me3 in *F. fujikuroi*, serving as a putative explanation for the lethality of *KMT1* deletion mutants in this species. If this is indeed true awaits further proof. Moreover, it is noteworthy to mention that some histone marks are more important (H3K27me3) for NP biosynthesis than others (H3K9me3). Here, H3K27me3 is predominantly installed over fungal BGCs involved in the biosynthesis of a large number of NPs. Partial removal and removal of facultative heterochromatin in *F. fujikuroi* and *F. proliferatum*, respectively, as well as for the distant relative *F. graminearum* led to the expression of a large number of BGCs normally silent under laboratory conditions^[34, 95, 96] (Paper V).

Now arises the question, how can fungi partially remove facultative heterochromatin to utilize a distinct set of genes? In plants and mammals alike a group of so-called JmjC-domain-containing histone demethylases facilitate the demethylation of H3K27me3^[131]. Thus far within the genus *Fusarium*, only two JmjC-domain-containing proteins were thoroughly characterized *i.e.*, Kdm4 and Kdm5, responsible for the demethylation of histone H3 lysine 36 trimethylation (H3K36me3) and the trimethylation of histone H3 lysine 4 (H3K4me3), in *F. fujikuroi* and *F. graminearum*^[97, 100, 132]. Still, there is no proof or evidence that a JmjC-domain-containing protein can facilitate H3K27-demethylation in filamentous fungi. Recently we were able to show that another chromatin regulatory mechanism is involved in the expression of a set of genes residing in facultative heterochromatin in *F. fujikuroi*, *i.e.*, the histone variant H2A.Z (Paper VI).

Incorporation of the prominent histone variant H2A.Z, in the chromatin scaffold, has been shown to have multifaceted consequences, especially for the transcriptional landscape^[111]. H2A.Z, is essential for higher organisms^[109], including *F. fujikuroi* and *F. graminearum*. However, various compensatory mutations in various chromatin-modifying enzymes and the

core histone H3, depending on the genetic background, rescued lethality in the latter ^[108] (Paper IV).

To study the function and role of H2A.Z in greater detail we were able to record for the first time the overall H2A.Z- and nucleosome distribution in *F. fujikuroi*. This revealed that H2A.Z is predominantly localized to the +1-nucleosome near the transcriptional start site (TSS) (Paper VI), as in several other model organisms ^[134]. Next to this presence of H2A.Z at the +1-nucleosome strongly correlates with positive gene transcription. Furthermore, we studied the overall distribution of the two opposing histone marks *i.e.*, H3K4me3 a hallmark of active gene transcription, and H3K27me3 major facilitator of gene silencing in various filamentous fungi, including *Fusarium* ^[135]. While we could not detect any crosstalk between H2A.Z and H3K4me3 or H3K27me3 as proposed for several model organisms ^[114, 116], we detected that co-localization of H2A.Z and H3K27me3 poises facultative heterochromatin for gene transcription ^[133] (Paper VI). This finding is especially intriguing since there are no mechanisms described facilitating gene expression in facultative heterochromatin in filamentous fungi yet. The reason for this could be the stabilizing effect of H2A.Z incorporation at the +1-nucleosome, thus making the nucleosome-depleted region (NDR) accessible for the transcriptional machinery. However, to unequivocally connect this phenomenon with the incorporation of H2A.Z at the +1-nucleosome, further research has to be performed. Still, there is no consensus on how gene expression in facultative heterochromatin is controlled in filamentous fungi. If gene expression is facilitated by the mere removal of H3K27me3 through demethylation, the eviction of whole nucleosome units to expose certain DNA regions, the stabilization of NDRs by H2A.Z or other proteins, or by even other still unknown mechanisms, or yet a sheer combination of different regulatory circuits, remain still elusive. Moreover, functional characterization of the histone variant H2A.Z by depletion or overexpression revealed that H2A.Z is not a prerequisite for establishing wild-type-like patterns of H3K4me3 or H3K27me3. This is in marked contrast to *N. crassa* where H2A.Z is required for normal patterns of H3K27me3 ^[113]. Similar observations were also made in embryonic stem cells ^[114, 136]. Next to this, H2A.Z is not vital for NP biosynthesis in *F. fujikuroi*, and only minor variations in NP gene expression and biosynthesis were observed. However, the H2A.Z depletion mutant revealed that H2A.Z is essential for fungal growth and conidiogenesis, which is not surprising taking into account that H2A.Z is essential in *Fusarium* ^[133] (Paper VI).

1.7 Summary and Conclusions

The genus *Fusarium* is widely distributed and includes a huge portfolio of genetically diverse fungal species with versatile ecological roles. Within this genus, the FFSC has a central role in agriculture as it harbors many economically important species able to cause disastrous plant diseases on staple crops and horticultural plants. On top of that, fusaria are producers of a plethora of NPs, including potent mycotoxins. Here, regular dietary exposure to such can result in severe adverse health effects in humans and livestock alike. The production of fungal NPs underlies a complex gene regulatory network involving the chromatin structure. Chromatin is not only the mere basic packaging form of DNA in eukaryotes, but it also serves as a dynamic template for all DNA-dependent processes including the transcriptional machinery. Therefore, the chromatin scaffold can respond to various environmental and developmental stimuli and with that regulate the exposure or compaction of the underlying DNA, which may lead to gene transcription or gene silencing, respectively. Such processes are mediated by various chromatin regulatory circuits, including histone marks, histone variants, DNA methylation, or large ATP-dependent chromatin-modifying enzymes.

Within this work, we could show that facultative heterochromatin (H3K27me3) is more important than constitutive heterochromatin (H3K9me3) for fungal development and NP biosynthesis. Yet, we could utilize mutants lacking the H3K9me3-specific methyltransferase Kmt1 to pin, FPY and FMNs, two NPs prior not known to be produced by members of the FFSC, to *F. mangiferae*. Next, we determined the responsible key enzymes and elucidated and functionally characterized the BGCs involved in the biosynthesis of both FPY and FMNs. Furthermore, we could reveal that both BGCs are also present in the genomes of other *Fusarium* species and with that NPs are not universally expressed, even if species are nearly related. This data not only points toward unique chromatin landscapes but also environmental cues required to trigger NP biosynthesis. One reason for this could be the different lifestyles of different *Fusarium* species. Next to this, we were finally able to report the crosstalk between constitutive (H3K9me3) and facultative heterochromatin (H3K27me3) also in this genus. Moreover, as the molecular mechanisms underlying the expression of genes covered by facultative heterochromatin in filamentous are still largely enigmatic, we revealed that incorporation of the prominent histone variant H2A.Z, can stabilize the +1-nucleosome and thus facilitate gene expression in normally silent facultative heterochromatic regions.

Following, we determined that H2A.Z is involved but not essential for fungal NP biosynthesis, but since the removal of H2A.Z is lethal in *Fusarium*, the presence of H2A.Z is vital for fungal physiology and/or development.

To conclude, through this work, we were able to “entangle” parts of the unique chromatin regulatory cosmos and its role in fungal development and NP biosynthesis in various members of the FFSC. As we could shed light on only some parts of this regulatory network, within this genus, still some fundamental questions remain to be answered in the future. Here, the still largely elusive mechanisms behind making facultative heterochromatin accessible are tempting to investigate, especially with the respect to unearthing the largely hidden chemical diversity within this genus. However, we could demonstrate that the chromatin structure and its associated enzymes involved in its modifications serve as a powerful tool not only to study fungal fitness but also for dissecting the biosynthesis of (cryptic) NPs. Thus, it is of utmost importance to study and understand chromatin regulatory mechanisms in fungal plant pathogens not only to invent novel cropping strategies but also to promote more resilient agriculture. This further reduces mycotoxin contamination and thus increases food and feed safety.

1.8 References

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2 Publications

2.1 Paper I

Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, A.K., Lünne, F., Kalinina, S.A., Strauss, J., Humpf, H., & Studt, L. (2021). Biosynthesis of Fusapyrone Depends on the H3K9 Methyltransferase, FmKmt1, in *Fusarium mangiferae*. *Frontiers in Fungal Biology*. doi: 10.3389/ffunb.2021.671796. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/ffunb.2021.671796/full>. **published**

Declaration of authorship:

Conceptualization	Investigation	Formal analysis	Writing – review & editing
Lena Studt, Anna K. Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, Joseph Strauss, Hans-Ulrich Humpf	Anna K. Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, Friederike Lünne, Svetlana Kalinina	Anna K. Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, Friederike Lünne, Svetlana Kalinina, Joseph Strauss, Hans-Ulrich Humpf, Lena Studt,	Anna K. Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, Friederike Lünne, Lena Studt

2.2 Paper II

Atanasoff-Kardjaleff, A.K., & Studt, L. (2022). Secondary Metabolite Gene Regulation in Mycotoxigenic *Fusarium* Species: A Focus on Chromatin. *Toxins*, 14. doi: 10.3390/toxins14020096. <https://www.mdpi.com/2072-6651/14/2/96>. **published**

Declaration of authorship:

Conceptualization	Writing— original draft	Writing – review & editing	Visualization	Funding acquisition
Anna K. Atanasoff- Kardjaleff, Lena Studt	Anna K. Atanasoff- Kardjaleff, Lena Studt	Anna K. Atanasoff- Kardjaleff	Anna K. Atanasoff- Kardjaleff	Lena Studt

2.3 Paper III

Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, A.K., Seidl, B., Steinert, K., Daniliuc, C.G., Schuhmacher, R., Humpf, H., Kalinina, S.A., & Studt-Reinhold, L. (2022). Biosynthesis of the Isocoumarin Derivatives Fusamarins is Mediated by the PKS8 Gene Cluster in *Fusarium*. *ChemBioChem*, 24. doi: 10.1002/cbic.202200342. <https://chemistry-europe.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/cbic.202200342>. **published**

Declaration of authorship:

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Anna K. Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, Lena Studt-Reinhold	Anna K. Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, Bernhard Seidl, Katharina Steinert, Constantin G. Daniliuc, Svetlana Kalinina	Anna K. Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, Bernhard Seidl, Katharina Steinert, Constantin G. Daniliuc, Svetlana Kalinina, Rainer Schuhmacher, Hans-Ulrich Humpf, Lena Studt-Reinhold	Anna K. Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, Lena Studt-Reinhold
Writing – original draft	Writing – review & editing		
Anna K. Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, Lena Studt-Reinhold	Anna K. Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, Lena Studt-Reinhold, Svetlana Kalinina, Rainer Schuhmacher, Hans-Ulrich Humpf		

2.4 Paper IV

Chen, Z., Zehraoui, E., **Atanasoff-Kardjaleff, A.K.**, Strauss, J., Studt, L., & Pons, N. (2020). Effect of H2A.Z deletion is rescued by compensatory mutations in *Fusarium graminearum*. *PLoS Genetics*, 16. doi: 10.1371/journal.pgen.1009125. <https://journals.plos.org/plosgenetics/article?id=10.1371/journal.pgen.1009125>. **published**

Declaration of authorship:

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Joseph Strauss, Lena Studt	Zhenhui Chen, Nadia Pons	Zhenhui Chen, Enric Zehraoui, Anna K. Atanasoff-Kardjaleff.	Enric Zehraoui, Nadia Pons.	Enric Zehraoui, Joseph Strauss, Lena Studt, Nadia Pons
Validation	Visualization	Writing – original draft	Writing – review & editing	
Zhenhui Chen, Anna K. Atanasoff-Kardjaleff, Lena Studt, Nadia Pons	Zhenhui Chen, Nadia Pons.	Zhenhui Chen, Nadia Pons.	Anna K. Atanasoff-Kardjaleff, Joseph Strauss, Lena Studt, Nadia Pons.	

2.5 Paper V

Studt-Reinhold, L., **Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, A.K.**, Berger, H., Petersen, C., Bachleitner, S., Sulyok, M., Fischle, A., Humpf, H., Kalinina, S., & Søndergaard, T. (2024). H3K27me3 is vital for fungal development and secondary metabolite gene silencing, and substitutes for the loss of H3K9me3 in the plant pathogen *Fusarium proliferatum*. *PLOS Genetics*, 20. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgen.1011075>. **published**

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Lena Studt-Reinhold	Harald Berger, Celine Petersen	Lena Studt-Reinhold, Anna K. Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, Harald Berger, Celine Petersen, Michael Sulyok.	Lena Studt-Reinhold, Anna K. Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, Celine Petersen, Simone Bachleitner, Michael Sulyok, Alica Fischle, Svetlana Kalinina.	Lena Studt-Reinhold
Funding acquisition	Project administration	Resources	Software	Supervision
Lena Studt-Reinhold	Lena Studt-Reinhold	Lena Studt-Reinhold, Hans-Ulrich Humpf, Teis Esben Søndergaard	Harald Berger, Celine Petersen	Lena Studt-Reinhold, Svetlana Kalinina, Teis Esben Søndergaard
Validation	Visualization	Writing – original draft	Writing – review & editing	
Lena Studt-Reinhold, Anna K. Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, Harald Berger, Svetlana Kalinina	Lena Studt-Reinhold, Anna K. Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, Harald Berger	Lena Studt-Reinhold, Anna K. Atanasoff-Kardjalieff	Harald Berger, Celine Petersen, Simone Bachleitner, Michael Sulyok, Alica Fischle, Hans-Ulrich Humpf, Svetlana Kalinina, Teis Esben Søndergaard	

2.6 Paper VI

Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, A.K., Berger, H., Steinert, K., Janevska, S., Ponts, N., Humpf, H.-U., Kalinina, S. & Studt-Reinhold, L. Incorporation of the histone variant H2A.Z counteracts gene silencing mediated by H3K27 trimethylation in *Fusarium fujikuroi*. *Epigenetics & Chromatin*, **in revision**

Declaration of authorship:

Conceptualization	Investigation	Data analysis	Writing – original draft	Writing – review & editing
Anna K. Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, Lena Studt-Reinhold,	Anna K. Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, Katharina Steinert, Slavica Janevska	Anna K. Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, Harald Berger, Katharina Steinert, Slavica Janevska, Hans-Ulrich Humpf, Svetlana Kalinina, Lena Studt-Reinhold	Anna K. Atanasoff-Kardjalieff	Anna K. Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, Harald Berger, Katharina Steinert, Slavica Janevska, Svetlana Kalinina, Hans-Ulrich Humpf, Lena Studt-Reinhold

Appendix A: Academic CV

LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

Studt-Reinhold, L., **Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, A.K.**, Berger, H., Petersen, C., Bachleitner, S., Sulyok, M., Fischle, A., Humpf, H.-U., Kalinina, S., & Sondergaard, T. (2024). H3K27me3 is vital for fungal development and secondary metabolite gene silencing, and substitutes for the loss of H3K9me3 in the plant pathogen *Fusarium proliferatum*. *PLOS Genetics*, 20.

Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, A.K., Seidl, B., Steinert, K., Daniliuc, C.G., Schuhmacher, R., Humpf, H., Kalinina, S.A., & Studt-Reinhold, L. (2022). Biosynthesis of the Isocoumarin Derivatives Fusamarins is Mediated by the PKS8 Gene Cluster in *Fusarium*. *ChemBioChem*, 24.

Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, A.K., & Studt, L. (2022). Secondary Metabolite Gene Regulation in Mycotoxigenic *Fusarium* Species: A Focus on Chromatin. *Toxins*, 14.

Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, A.K., Lünne, F., Kalinina, S.A., Strauss, J., Humpf, H., & Studt, L. (2021). Biosynthesis of Fusapyrone Depends on the H3K9 Methyltransferase, FmKmt1, in *Fusarium mangiferae*. *Frontiers in Fungal Biology*.

Chen, Z., Zehraoui, E., **Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, A.K.**, Strauss, J., Studt, L., & Ponts, N. (2020). Effect of H2A.Z deletion is rescued by compensatory mutations in *Fusarium graminearum*. *PLoS Genetics*, 16.

Espinosa, M.J., Blanco, A.C., Schmidgall, T., **Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, A.K.**, Kappelmeyer, U., Tischler, D., Pieper, D.H., Heipieper, H.J., & Eberlein, C. (2020). Toward Biorecycling: Isolation of a Soil Bacterium That Grows on a Polyurethane Oligomer and Monomer. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 11.

PUBLICATIONS IN REVISION

Steinert, K., **Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, A.K.**, Messner, E., Gorfer, M., Niehaus, E.-M., Humpf, H.-U., Studt-Reinhold, L & Kalinina, S.A. Unraveling the potential of *Stachybotrys chartarum*: Accessing novel polyketide synthase gene clusters. *Fungal Genetics and Biology*

Atanasoff-Kardjalieff, A.K., Berger, H., Steinert, K., Janevska, S., Ponts, N., Humpf, H.-U., Kalinina, S. & Studt-Reinhold, L. Incorporation of the histone variant H2A.Z counteracts gene silencing mediated by H3K27 trimethylation in *Fusarium fujikuroi*. *Epigenetics & Chromatin*

PROJECT LEADS

HistoVar: Role of the histone variant H2A.Z in pathogenic *Fusarium* species

Funded by the Austrian Science Funds (FWF): I 3911-B29

Sep 2023 - Dec 2023

THESIS SUPERVISION

Master Thesis, Feb 2022 - Aug 2022

Thesis title - Molecular characterization of the cryptic polyketide synthase 16 gene cluster in *Fusarium*

Bachelor Thesis, Jun 2019 - Sep 2019

Thesis title - Role of the histone 3 lysine 9 methyltransferase Kmt1 in *Fusarium mangiferae* development and secondary metabolism

TUTORING & TEACHING

Sigmund Freud University Vienna | AUSTRIA

Summer- & Winter semester 2022 / Summer semester 2023

Research practical courses: Basic methods of genetic engineering & Genetic engineering II

VOLUNTEERING

Forschungsfest 2022, Sep 2022 | Vienna, AUSTRIA

How does the cow get into the computer? Project of AgriGenomics PhD students to give insights into the doctoral program

Long Night of Research 2022, May 2022 | Tulln an der Donau, AUSTRIA

What does the inside of a fungal cell look like? Using VR goggles, the inside of a fungal cell is explained to adults and children

CONFERENCES AND SEMINARS

16th European Fusarium Seminar, Jun 2023 | Rome, ITALY

Oral presentation - The histone variant H2A.Z: Insights in its role in gene regulation in the phytopathogen *F. fujikuroi*

16th European Conference on Fungal Genetics (16th ECFG), Mar 2023 | Innsbruck, AUSTRIA

Poster presentation - Novel insights into the role of the histone variant H2A.Z in the plant pathogen *Fusarium fujikuroi*

Fusarium Workshop (16th ECFG) Mar 2023 | Innsbruck, AUSTRIA

Oral presentation - The *Fusarium* PKS8 gene cluster facilitates biosynthesis of the dihydroisocoumarin derivatives fusamarins

14th Symposium of the VAAM Special Group 'Biology and Biotechnology of Fungi', Sep 2022 | Kaiserslautern, GERMANY

Poster presentation - Biosynthesis of the dihydroisocoumarins fusamarins is mediated by the PKS8 gene cluster in *Fusarium*

31st Fungal Genetics Conference Mar 2022 | Pacific Grove, UNITED STATES OF AMERICA

Poster presentation - Regulation and product identification of FmPKS8, a so far cryptic PKS in *F. mangiferae*

42nd Mycotoxin Workshop, May 2021 | Münster, GERMANY

Oral presentation (online) - Fusapyrone biosynthesis in *Fusarium mangiferae* depends on the histone methyltransferase FmKmt1 involved in H3K9me3

15th European Fusarium Seminar, May 2021 | Ghent, BELGIUM

Oral presentation (online) - FmKmt1 involved in H3K9me3 regulates expression of secondary metabolite gene clusters in *Fusarium mangiferae*

13th conference of the VAAM special group 'Molecular Biology of Fungi', Sep 2019 | Göttingen, GERMANY

Poster presentation - Role of the histone 3 lysine 9 methyltransferase Kmt1 in fungal development and secondary metabolism in different *Fusarium* spp.

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